

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF AUTOIMMUNE THROMBOCYTOPENIA**Taralunga Victoria,***Student, Faculty of General Medicine
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State University of Medicine and Pharmacy „Nicolae Testemitanu”
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau***Abstract**

A descriptive, retrospective study was carried out in which the clinical manifestations and treatment results were analyzed in 45 patients with the diagnosis of autoimmune idiopathic thrombocytopenia, who were on record in the Hematology Department and the Consultative Center of the Oncology Institute during the years 2017- 2022. The study showed that idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia was determined more frequently in people aged 30-49 years (46.6%) and predominated in women (65%), and the hemorrhagic syndrome was more frequently manifested by petechiae (62.2%), ecchymosis (55.5%), less often - epistaxis (26.66%) and gingivoragia (24.4%). In most cases (71.2%), in the general blood analysis the platelets were solitary, less often the platelets constituted $20-50 \times 10^9/l$ (28.8%) and in the bone marrow examination more frequently (51.6%) an increase in megakaryocytes with a decrease in platelets was determined, and in 22.5% of cases with a decrease in platelets, a decrease in megakaryocytes also occurred. It was also determined that treatment efficacy was higher when splenectomy was performed. The 5-year progression-free survival of patients with splenectomy was 91%, as opposed to progression-free survival of 17% for patients treated with glucocorticoids.

Keywords: idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia, hemorrhagic syndrome, treatment.

Introduction

Autoimmune thrombocytopenia or idiopathic thrombocytopenic purpura (ITP) is a pathology that is part of hemorrhagic diatheses, which is acquired as a result of a complex immune process. It is characterized by the reduction of platelets, caused by their increased destruction, and can be asymptomatic or accompanied by manifestations of bleeding in the mucosa and skin of varying severity [6]. ITP can occur in patients of both sexes and all ages. It does not show racial characteristics [2]. According to research conducted in Europe, the incidence of ITP is increasing in elderly patients. The idea is supported by the results of studies carried out in the UK and Denmark, which denote the increase in the incidence of ITP in people aged >60 years [4]. The diagnosis of ITP will be established on the basis of clinical manifestations, the results of the general analysis of peripheral blood, the results of the bone marrow examination and the exclusion of pathologies that can cause secondary autoimmune thrombocytopenia [3]. The treatment of idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia is aimed at combating antibodies with an increase in the number of platelets. Several treatment strategies are known. Initially, they opt for non-invasive methods such as corticosteroids, intravenous immunoglobulins, monoclonal antibodies, thrombopoietin receptor antagonists. In the absence of effectiveness of conservative treatment, splenectomy is chosen [5].

Aim of the study

Study of the clinical hematological aspects and the results of the treatment of idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia.

Materials and methods

A descriptive, retrospective study was carried out in which the clinical manifestations and treatment results were analyzed in 45 patients with the diagnosis of autoimmune idiopathic thrombocytopenia, who were on record in the Hematology Department and the Consultative Center of the Oncology Institute during the years 2017- 2022. Patients were selected for the sample based on inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria: patients with a confirmed diagnosis of ITP; age > 18 years; the possibility of monitoring patients. Exclusion criteria: age < 18 years; positive HBV, HCV markers; positive HIV test; pathology confirming secondary ITP; lack of possibility of monitoring.

The diagnosis was established on the basis of the clinical and paraclinical examination (general blood analysis, bone marrow examination). Age characteristics, clinical manifestations, hematological changes and treatment results were analyzed.

The treatment response was assessed based on the following classification: complete response – if the number of platelets increased $>100 \times 10^9/l$; with response - in cases when the platelet count is $30-100 \times 10^9/l$ or at least double the primary platelet count; no response – in cases when the number of platelets does not exceed $30 \times 10^9/l$ or is lower than twice the value of the number of platelets [1].

Results

The distribution of patients according to the age at which the diagnosis was established showed that idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia developed more frequently in people aged 30-49 years (44.6%) followed by the 18-29 age group and 50-70 years (28.8% and 26.6%, respectively) (table 1).

Distribution of patients with idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia depending on age		
Age	The number of patients	Frequency (%)
18-29	13	28,8
30-49	20	44,6
50-70	12	26,6
Total	45	100

The distribution of patients according to age and sex demonstrated that idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia in all age groups was more often determined in women than in men (figure 1). The ratio of approximately 3:1 was established. Especially, the increase in

the rate of idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia was observed in women in the age group of 50-70 years in which 11 of 12 patients were identified - women (91.7%) and only one man (8.3%).

Figure 1. Distribution of patients with idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia according to age and sex

The analysis of patients' complaints revealed that the most common clinical manifestations were petechiae (62.2%), ecchymosis (55.5%), epistaxis (26.6%), followed by gingivoragia (24.4%) and weakness (22.2%). Less frequently there were allegations of

heavy menstruation (13.3%) which is specific to women of childbearing age. The rarest signs that have been recorded are hematuria (2.2%) and melena (2.2%) (figure 2).

Figure 2. Frequency of clinical symptoms in patients with idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia

At researching the results of general blood tests, attention was drawn to the number of platelets, the hemoglobin index, the number of erythrocytes and leukocytes. Thrombocytopenias were detected in all cases. In

13 (28.8%) patients the number of platelets varied between $20-50 \times 10^9/l$, and in 32 (71.2%) cases solitary platelets were identified (figure 3).

Figure 3. Distribution of patients according to platelet count

The hemoglobin index and the number of erythrocytes were within the normal range in 29 (82.3%) patients. Anemia was determined in 16 (21.3%) cases, of

which grade I anemia was identified in 13 (13.3%) patients and grade II anemia - in 3 (4.4%) cases (figure 4).

Figure 4. Distribution of patients according to hemoglobin and erythrocyte count indices

The analysis of the results of the bone marrow examination showed that in 16 (51.6%) cases the increase of megakaryocytes with the reduction of platelets was determined. In 8 (25.8%) patients megakaryocytes -

normal and platelets reduced. In 7 (22.6%) cases there was a reduction of megakaryocytes and platelets (figure 5).

Figure 5. The results of the bone marrow examination

For the first line of treatment, glucocorticoid therapy at a dose of 1mg/kg was applied to all patients. The analysis of the effectiveness of the treatment of idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia with glucocorticoids showed that the positive response, which was

manifested by the suppression of the hemorrhagic syndrome and the increase in the number of platelets, was determined in 43 (95.6%) patients. In 2 (4.4%) cases no positive response to the administered treatment was obtained. Out of 43 patients with a complete positive ef-

fect on the background of glucocorticoid treatment, relapses developed in 37 (86.0%) cases. Remissions achieved after glucocorticoid therapy were short-lived and lasted up to 12 months.

Monoclonal antibody therapy - rituximab was applied to 5 patients with relapses after glucocorticoid treatment. In 3 (60%) cases a complete positive response was determined, but in 2 (40%) patients efficacy was lacking.

In 36 (89.7%) patients with relapses after glucocorticoid therapy, splenectomy was performed. Analy-

sis of splenectomy results showed that complete positive response occurred in 35 (97.3%) cases. The lack of efficacy from splenectomy occurred in only one patient (2.7%). Relapse after splenectomy was recorded in only one patient.

The 5-year progression-free survival of patients with idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia after splenectomy was high and constituted 91%. But the survival in the same terms of patients with a positive complete response after glucocorticoid therapy was equal to only 17% (figure 6).

Figure 6. Progression-free survival of patients with complete response autoimmune thrombocytopenia

Thus, it was determined that the immediate and long-term results of the treatment of patients with idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia were higher in cases of performing splenectomy as second-line therapy.

Conclusions

1. Idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia was determined more frequently in people aged 30-49 years (46.6%) and predominated in women (65%).

2. The hemorrhagic syndrome in idiopathic autoimmune thrombocytopenia was more frequently manifested by petechiae (62.2%), ecchymosis (55.5%), less often - epistaxis (26.66%) and gingivoragia (24.4%).

3. In most cases (71.2%), in the general blood analysis the platelets were solitary, less often the platelets constituted $20-50 \times 10^9/l$ (28.8%) and in the bone marrow examination more frequently (51.6%) an increase in megakaryocytes with a decrease in platelets was determined, and in 22.5% of cases with a decrease in platelets, a decrease in megakaryocytes also occurred.

4. Treatment efficacy was higher when splenectomy was performed. The 5-year survival of patients with splenectomy was 91%, as opposed to progression-free survival of 17% for patients treated with glucocorticoids.

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